

Investigation of the inflammatory role of miR-21, miR-129, and miR-217 in ovarian cancer

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Abstract

Background: The highest mortality rate among gynecological cancers, especially in metastatic stages, is associated with ovarian cancer (OC), the eighth most common cancer in women globally. Therefore, screening measures that target early curable stages of the disease are crucial. Because of their excellent stability and changes specific to a disease, microRNA (miRNA) molecules are emerging as potentially useful diagnostic tools for OC.

Material and Method: One hundred sixty participants were enrolled, comprising eighty OC patients diagnosed based on World Health Organization (WHO) criteria and eighty healthy controls. Quantitative real-time reverse transcription-PCR (qRT-PCR) was used to examine the expression levels of miRNAs, namely miR-21, miR-129, and miR-217. Furthermore, the degree of NF-κB expression was evaluated to clarify its correlation with the miRNAs under investigation.

Result: Our results showed that, in comparison to healthy individuals, OC patients had lower blood levels of miR-129 ($P < 0.05$) and miR-217 ($P < 0.05$) and higher serum levels of miR-21 ($P < 0.05$). Moreover, a noteworthy negative correlation was found between miR-129, miR-217, and NF-κB, but a significant positive association was found between miR-21 and NF-κB. The study of the receiver operating characteristic curve revealed that the AUC values for miR-21 (0.89), miR-129 (0.84), and miR-217 (0.86) were considerably higher.

Conclusion: According to our research, the anti-inflammatory miR-129 and miR-217, as well as the inflammatory miR-21, may function as noninvasive biomarkers for the diagnosis of OC.

Keywords: Ovarian Cancer, miR-21, miR-129, miR-217, NF-κB.

1. Introduction

According to the American Cancer Society, ovarian cancer (OC) is a fatal gynecological malignancy. Unfortunately, over 75% of OC cases are diagnosed in advanced stages with a widely metastatic pattern. Apparently, clinical signs are missing in the

early stages, and establishing diagnostic biomarkers is strongly required for early diagnosis of the disease (1).

Ovulation and postmenopausal events are most likely associated with increased OC risks through inflammatory mechanisms. (2).

Exposure of the epithelial cells to inflammatory mediators like cytokines, reactive oxygen species, prostaglandins, and growth factors at sites of inflammation can cause increased cell division along with genetic and epigenetic changes. Through unchecked cell proliferation and malignant transformation of the cells, these alterations lead to the development of cancer (3). NF- κ B pathway contributes to controlling different cellular processes such as pro-inflammatory cytokine production and apoptosis inhibition. This pathway has involved the progression of multiple blood and solid malignancies and control. It has recently been reported that the OC metastatic capacity was enhanced via activation of the NF- κ B pathway by inducing M1 macrophage-conditioned media and pro-inflammatory cytokines secretion (4).

Microscopic non-coding RNAs, or miRNAs, are small RNAs that do not code for any protein. They mainly inhibit the synthesis of proteins by binding specifically to messenger RNA (mRNA), usually in the 3'-UTR region. (5, 6). Also, the stability of miRNAs in different biological fluids and storage conditions has made them useful diagnostic biomarkers and therapeutic goals for various cancers. Additionally, miRNAs are considered to play a role in developing human malignancies, including OC.

Along with the overexpression of Mir-21 in most cancers and its implication in tumorigenesis, it is also reported that Mir-21 has a dynamic role in inflammation and acceleration of injury responses. In this line, a remarkable decrease in ovarian and prostatic cancer cell proliferation and invasion was identified following miR-21 inhibition (7). According to J Cao *et al.*, assessing exosomal miR-21-5p role in OC cells showed promotion in OC cell proliferation, migration, and invasion predominantly via CDK6 regulation (8). As a result, miR-21 is crucial to the pathogenesis of OC.

MiR-129-5p, another microRNA located on chromosome 7q32.1, is known to play a critical role in the development of tumors. Reduced inflammatory response has been linked to increased expression of miR-129-5p (9). It has been shown in recent research to have an inhibitory effect on the survival, proliferation, and tumorigenicity of ovarian cancer (OC) cells. This has established a link between the malignant growth of OC cells and the downregulation of miR-129-5p, which results in poor survival outcomes (10). Furthermore, in human OC cell lines, miR-217 functions as a tumor suppressor by directly targeting CUL4B and inhibits the Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway, cell migration, invasion, and apoptosis enhancement (11). Moreover, miR-217 directly inhibits OC cells' production and expression of IL-6, which affects M2 macrophage polarization and promotes tumor growth (12).

The purpose of this study was to examine the potential usefulness of miR-21, miR-129, and miR-217 as reliable biomarkers for the

diagnosis of early-stage ovarian cancer. The study aimed to determine the function of these three molecules in the process of inflammation by comparing their expression levels in OC patients and healthy individuals, with an emphasis on NF- κ B gene expression.

2. Material and Methods

Blood sampling and RNA extraction

Blood samples from 80 patients with ovarian cancer (OC) and 80 age-matched healthy controls were taken using red vacuum tubes. The samples were centrifuged for 15 min at four °C at 4500 rpm. Serum samples were also obtained in order to extract total RNA. Total RNA, including small and long non-coding RNA (ncRNA), was extracted from the sera using Norgen's total RNA purification kit (Norgen Biotek Corporation, Canada) and following the manufacturer's instructions. Using a Thermo Fisher Scientific NanoDrop spectrophotometer, the amount of RNA was measured. The 260/280 and 260/230 ratios were used to determine the acceptable limits for RNA purity confirmation, and they were found to be 1.8–2.2 and 2–2.2, respectively. The Shahid Sadoughi University of Medical Sciences University ethics committee (IR.SSU.MEDICINE.REC.1396.220) approved this study in compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki's tenets. Additionally, every patient who took part gave their written consent.

cDNA synthesis

Using an Eppendorf Mastercycler Gradient device (Hamburg, Germany) and the Revert Aid First Strand cDNA synthesis kit (Thermo Scientific, Vilnius, Lithuania), 1 μ g total extracted RNA, random hexamer, and oligo-dT primers were used for each reaction in the cDNA synthesis of NF- κ B. The BONmiR kit was used to synthesize cDNA for miR-21, miR-129, miR-217, and SNORD 47 (used as a housekeeping gene).

Real-time PCR

Using the Rotor-Gene 6000 equipment (Corbett, Concorde, NSW, Australia) and the SYBR Green technique, qRT-PCR reactions were carried out. For internal control, NF- κ B, and miRNAs (miR-21, miR-205, and miR-217), each reaction contained a 15 μ l with 1 μ l cDNA, 6.25 μ l 2 \times qPCR master mix, 0.5 μ l particular forward primer, and 0.5 μ l universal reverse primer. Enzyme activation (one cycle, 95°C, two min), denaturation (40 cycles, 95°C, five seconds), and annealing/extension (40 cycles, 60°C, thirty seconds) were the temperature conditions for miRNA amplification. The average CT value was used for analysis, and all real-time PCR studies included controls without template (cDNA) to reduce the possibility of contamination.

Table .1

	Sequence 5'-3'	Assassin number	Location of primer	Intron/exon
NF-κB	F: CTTCAGAATGGCAGAAGATG R: GCTCTAATATTTGAAGGTATGGG	NM_001165412	501-520 633-655	Exone
GAPDH	F: GTCTCCTCTGACTTCAACAGCG R: ACCACCCTGTTGCTGTAGCCAA	NM_002046.7	866-887 975-996	Exone
miR-21	ACGTGTTAGCTTATCAGACTG	NR_029493	8 – 22	
miR-205	CTTGTCTTCATTCCACCGGA	NR_029622.1	30-50	
miR-217	TACTGCATCAGGAAGTACTGGA	NR_029630.1	35-57	
SNORD 47	ATCACTGTAAAACCGTTCCA	NR_002746.1	42-61	
Universal reverse primers were acquired from Bonyakhteh Company (Iran)				

Statistical analysis

The 2^{-ΔΔCt} technique was used to examine the real-time PCR data, and the results are presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD). The significance of the differences in gene expression between ovarian cancer (OC) and healthy control groups was evaluated using a t-test. Furthermore, Pearson's correlation analysis was utilized to examine the connections between the variables. For statistical significance, a P-value of less than 0.05 was used. For data analysis, Graph Pad, San Diego, California, USA, provided Prism 7.

3. Results

The 160 participants in the study were divided into 80 cases of ovarian cancer (OC) and 80 age- and sex-matched controls. Table 1 lists the individuals' demographic and underlying features, and Table 2 shows the oligonucleotide primer sequences used in the qRT-PCR investigation.

Evaluation of miR-21 expression in OC and association with NF-κB

The miR-21 relative expression was analyzed in both the OC and control samples, with U6 serving as an internal control. Our results showed that the miR-21 expression was considerably higher in OC samples than in controls (7.361 ± 0.3346 , n=80 versus 1.995 ± 0.359 , n = 80; $P < 0.05$). In addition, the relationship between miR-21 and NF-κB was evaluated in order to investigate miR-21's function in the inflammatory pathway, and the results showed a positive connection ($r = 0.4932$, $P < 0.05$).

Additionally, a receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis was carried out to evaluate the sensitivity and specificity of miR-21 in differentiating between OC and control samples. Given its 89% area under the curve (AUC) and $P < 0.05$, miR-21 appears to be a promising tumor marker for OC.

Evaluation of miR-129 expression in OC and association with NF-κB

MiR-129 expression levels in OC and control samples were analyzed, and the results showed that OC samples had significantly lower miR-129 expression than controls (0.2292 ± 0.009791 , n=80 versus 1.127 ± 0.05978 , n=80; $P < 0.05$) (Figure 1B). It was shown that miR-129 and NF-κB had a strong negative correlation (-0.5706 , $P < 0.05$). Furthermore, a ROC curve analysis was performed to evaluate the sensitivity and specificity of miR-129. The results indicated an AUC of 84% ($P < 0.0001$), indicating the potential of miR-129 as a tumor marker for OC.

Evaluation of miR-217 expression in OC and association with NF-κB

In both the OC and control samples, the relative expression of miR-217 was evaluated (Fig. 2a). Tumor samples had significantly lower miR-217 expression levels (0.1834 ± 0.004995 , n = 80) than non-tumor samples (1.056 ± 0.03848 , n = 80) ($P < 0.05$). A strong negative connection (-0.6457 , $P < 0.05$) was seen when miR-217 expression and NF-κB were examined. Based on the AUC, which was determined to be 86% ($P < 0.05$) to indicate its ability to distinguish OC from healthy persons, the diagnostic capacity of miR-217 expression was assessed.

Figure1: The relative expression levels of miR-21 (B), miR-129 (D), and miR-217 (F) in serum samples from patients with ovarian cancer (OC) and healthy controls are shown. The study of the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve indicates that the area under the curve for miR-21 (A), miR-129 (C), and miR-217 (E) is 89%, 84%, and 86%, respectively. The displayed results show the average relative mRNA expression measured by RT-PCR. Standard deviation is indicated by vertical error bars.

4. DISCUSSION

The diagnostic techniques for OC are mainly based on pelvic and para-clinical examinations, including abdominal and transvaginal ultrasonography and pelvic mass biopsy. Currently, the most common biomarker for OC diagnosis is the cancer antigen 125 (CA-125). In this line, highly conserved non-coding miRNAs are among the biomarkers that can potentially be considered for early diagnosis and monitoring of different types of cancers. In order to compare OC tumor samples to control samples, the expression levels of miR-21, miR-129, and miR-217 were examined in this work.

Pro-inflammatory signals from activated immune cells are considered to result in the enhanced expression of miR-21. In line with miR-21 activation with immune cells, this miRNA is dysregulated in but is not limited to, psoriasis, allergic airway inflammation, heart disease, osteoarthritis, and cancer (13). Also, it has been recently disclosed that in high glucose conditions, TGF β 1 can induce miR-21 via NF κ B activation. Moreover, it is reported that in human non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), miR-21 inhibition led to apoptosis induction via the PI3K/Akt/NF- κ B signaling pathway inhibition (14, 15). Additionally, according to X Lu et al., (16) inhibition of miR-21-5p in the ulcerative colitis (UC) rat model mediated the IL-6/STAT3 pathway to decrease inflammation and apoptosis in RAW264.7 cells, suggesting miR-21-5p as a therapeutic goal in human UC. Our results in this investigation indicated a strong positive association between miR-21 and NF κ B expression levels. In line with previous studies, the findings of our study also suggest it is likely that miR-21, predominantly through induction of pro-inflammatory agents, plays a role in the progression of OC. Also, increased miR-21 gene expression in this study is supported by other studies that have reported increased levels of miR-21 in patients with OC compared to healthy individuals, which can be used as a potential diagnostic biomarker in this disease.

Recent findings demonstrated that LPS stimulation of podocytes inhibits miR-129 expression. It is also reported that miR-129 overexpression is a protective factor against LPS-induced podocyte damage, inflammation, and apoptosis, mainly mediated through HMGB1/TLRs/NF- κ B signaling (17). FBW7 is introduced as a novel E3 ubiquitin ligase for I κ B α , which activates the NF- κ B and inflammation. On the other hand, miR-129 is considered to negatively regulate the expression of FBW7, secondarily inhibit the NF- κ B pathway, and ameliorate inflammation of the intestine in Inflammatory Bowel Disease (18). Herein, the anti-inflammatory role of miR-129 in OC was determined by evaluating NF- κ B expression. Based on our results, we identified a negative correlation between miR-129 and NF- κ B. This suggests that the elevated expression of NF- κ B in OC cases aligns with the reduced levels of miR-129, consistent with the anti-inflammatory properties associated with miR-129. Therefore, it is plausible that miR-129 exerts inhibitory effects on OC cells by acting upstream in the NF- κ B activation pathway.

However, additional research is needed to delve deeper into the underlying mechanisms of this relationship.

A growing amount of research highlights the recurring dysregulation of miR-217 in a variety of cancer types, highlighting its critical function in the development and spread of cancer. A study by J Li et al. examined the biological roles of miR-217 in relation to epithelial ovarian cancer (EOC). MiR-217 was found to be expressed downregulated in both EOC tissues and cell lines. Furthermore, studies conducted in vitro showed that EOC cells overexpressing miR-217 inhibited colony formation cell proliferation and reduced cell invasion and migration. These outcomes were ascribed to miR-217's specific targeting of IGF1R (19). Likewise, our study showed downregulation in the miR-217 expression in human OC patients compared to the corresponding normal individuals, indicating a miR-217 remarkable role in OC pathogenesis. Additionally, to determine the miR-217 diagnostic value for OC, an ROC curve analysis was performed, and our data revealed that the AUC for miR-217 was significantly higher, with values of 0.86. These findings emphasize the potentially novel predictive value of the miR-217 as a tool for decision-making OC patients. Moreover, recent investigations strongly disclosed miR-217 modulation of anti-viral/bacterial immunity via NF- κ B and IRF3 signaling pathways mediated by TAK-1. Therefore, to assess the miR-217 involvement in the inflammatory processes of OC, we investigated the associations between miR-217 and NF- κ B. Interestingly, our results identified a remarkable negative relationship between miR-217 and NF- κ B. Therefore, miRNA-217 provides a promising therapeutic goal to inhibit the aberrant inflammatory factors in the OC early inflammatory state. Our results thus indicate a potential translational application of miR-217 in clinical practice.

5. Conclusion

In summary, these findings revealed that miR-21 expression increased in OC patients compared to healthy individuals. In addition, expression levels of miR-129 and miR-217 decreased in OC patients. Moreover, a significant relationship was observed between miR-21, miR-129, miR-217, and NF- κ B. These results indicate a critical role of these miRNAs in the pathophysiology of OC through inflammatory pathways and suggest potential miRNA-based treatment strategies.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors assert the absence of conflicts of interest, whether financial or otherwise.

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